

Effect of the Utilization of Home Language and Reading Ability of Grade One Pupils

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Abstract. This study seeks to determine the effect of the utilization of home language and reading ability of grade one pupils. This study makes use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Cockerel 2020). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study will be conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Oriental District, Division of Digos City. The subjects of this study will be the 60 grade one learners – 28 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 32 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of home language development program has increased the reading fluency of grade one pupils. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. home language 2. reading ability 3. grade one pupils

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1. Introduction

The use of one's native language presents a range of obstacles, such as variations in standards, inadequate assistance, shifting between languages, changes across generations, biases, loss of language proficiency, and limited resources. To tackle these issues effectively, a comprehensive approach involving community engagement, educational initiatives, policy adjustments, and cultural advocacy is often necessary to preserve and reinvigorate native languages. According to Ray (2020), home schooled students generally surpass their traditionally schooled counterparts in standardized tests and other academic measures, underscoring the importance of native language in homeschooling. As per Hoof (2020), youngsters hailing from households characterized by linguistic minority and low socioeconomic status (SES) tend to exhibit distinct early language trajectories. This underscores the importance of the linguistic environment within the home for fostering language acquisition and its impact on academic performance. De Houwer (2020) underscores the understanding of bilingual first language acquisition, incorporating the significance of the home setting in bolster-

ing children's mastery of two or more languages. Fishman (2020) examines the elements driving language shift and methods for counteracting language decline, stressing the crucial role of preserving home languages to safeguard linguistic diversity. Wei, L. (2020) delves into diverse aspects of bilingualism, encompassing language retention and change, language utilization across different contexts, and the familial and communal contributions to fostering bilingual growth. In (2020), the concept of translanguaging is introduced, underscoring the adaptable and lively manner in which bilingual individuals employ language. This underscores the significance of appreciating and respecting varied language behaviors, including those occurring within familial settings. Orellana, M. F. (2021) investigates the encounters of transnational children managing numerous languages and cultural environments, highlighting the family's role in passing down language and cultural traditions through generations. May, S. (2021) delves into the convergence of language, ethnicity, and politics, encompassing the impact of language policies on either fostering or detracting from linguistic diversity and the rights of minority languages. Ricento, T. (2020) provides a theoretical and historical examination of language planning and policy, highlighting the numerous socio-political factors influencing linguistic choices and practices within different societies. These insights shed light on the role of home language in sociopolitical contexts, the preservation of languages, the formation of identity, and language acquisition. It underscores the importance of recognizing and appreciating linguistic diversity within communities and families. The issue of literacy existed before the introduction of MTB-MLE, but it exacerbated during the execution of the language policy. It wasn't until November 2019 that the Department of Education addressed the issue through DepEd Memorandum No. 173, Series of 2019, (Challenge: Every Child a Reader), marking

the point at which the problem reached a critical level. Perfetti (2020) outlines the mental operations engaged in comprehending written text and the elements that foster the enhancement of reading abilities, including familiarity with words, recognition of speech sounds, and understanding sentence structure. Meanwhile, Stanovich introduces the notion of "Matthew effects" in reading, which denotes the compounding benefits or setbacks encountered by individuals stemming from their initial encounters with literacy and their proficiency in it. To exemplify the variations in academic achievements based on family socioeconomic status (SES), Sirin (2020) conducted a meta-analysis of scholarly papers exploring the correlation between socioeconomic status (SES) and academic performance, which encompasses reading proficiency among other factors. Sirin (2020) conducts a meta-analysis of research studies examining the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and academic achievement, including reading ability, highlighting the disparities in academic outcomes based on family SES. While there are other factors influencing the reading crisis, it's significant to observe that despite the expectation of enhanced reading skills through the MTB-MLE, students within the learning poverty bracket have undergone this program for three years yet continue to struggle with reading. Unlike private schools, which haven't adopted the MTB-MLE and continue to instruct primarily in English, their students face a disadvantage in regional competitions conducted in English ("Starting Where the Children Are: A Process Evaluation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Implementation," Philippine Institute for Development Studies). In the division of Digos City, reading comprehension is a persistent problem among elementary graders. They can decode but can't understand what they read. It creates a problem across subject areas. The researcher being a teacher explores an initiative of utiliz-

ing home language to make strong foundation in reading ability. Hence, this study.

2. Methodology

This study makes use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Cockerel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

2.1. Research Design—

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Oriental District, Division of Digos City. The subjects of this study will be the 60 grade one learners – 28 are from section A the controlled group and 32 are from section B which the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the test type questionnaire constructed by

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Dr Melanie P. Estacio, CESO VI, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Digos City and to the school principal concerned. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and to the principal of Dawis Elementary School, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. Af-

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and in-

the researcher. The test will cover the competencies in reading particularly those competencies that are least mastered by the learners. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25-item test eventually determine the reading comprehension skills of the research subjects. The pretest administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess the reading comprehension skills of grade four learners. On the hand, posttest administered to measure the effect of the treatment.

To determine the reading comprehension skills of grade one learners, the following continuum used based on DepEd rating system.

ter permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Dawis Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

terpretation the responses in this study. Mean used to describe the reading comprehension

Criteria for Student Performance Levels

Interval	Scale	Level and Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced: The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient: The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency: The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing: The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning: The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

skills of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pretest and posttest. T-test for uncorrelated samples used to test the significance of difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the experimental and

controlled groups. Eta square used to measure the magnitude of effect home reading strategy on the reading comprehension skills of grade one learners

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade five learners. The controlled group got the mean of 32.50 or Be-

ginning while the experimental group got the mean of 30.50 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	50	32.50	49.63	Beginning
Experimental Group	48	30.50	49.61	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Mol et al (2020) who said that home reading strategies provide opportunities for parent-child bonding and interaction. Shared book reading sessions promote positive parent-child relationships and create a supportive environment for literacy development (Bus et al., 1995; Sénéchal LeFevre, 2002). Engaging in home reading activities exposes children to a rich vocabulary and varied language structures, which contributes to the development of vocabulary knowledge and comprehension skills (Sénéchal LeFevre, 2002; Whitehurst et al., 1994). Children who participate in home reading activities often develop positive attitudes toward reading and view reading as an enjoyable and rewarding activity, which can foster a lifelong love of literature (Mol et al., 2018).

Home Reading Strategy refers to a structured approach or intervention designed to promote reading engagement and literacy development outside of the school setting, typically within the home environment. This strategy often involves encouraging parents or caregivers to actively support and facilitate reading activities with their children at home. The effects of implementing a home reading strategy can have several positive outcomes for children’s literacy skills, academic achievement, and overall development. Implementing a home reading strategy has been associated with significant improvements in children’s literacy skills, including phonemic awareness, vocabulary development, reading fluency, and comprehension (Sénéchal LeFevre, 2002; Senechal et al., 1998). Home reading strategies often lead to an increase in the frequency and duration of children’s reading activities at home. Regular engagement in reading promotes literacy growth and fosters

a lifelong love of reading (Sénéchal LeFevre, 2022).

Post Test Scores Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade one learners. The

controlled group got the mean of 33.80 or Approaching Proficiency while the experimental group gained the mean of 36.20 or Proficient.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	50	33.80	84.00	Approaching Proficiency
Experimental Group	48	36.20	90.05	Proficient

It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 5.80 from a mean rating of 30.40 to 36.20. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the statement in National Reading Panel (2020) which said that the effect of home reading strategies on children’s literacy development has been extensively studied in educational research. Implementing structured reading activities at home can have a significant impact on various aspects of children’s literacy skills, including reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and fluency. One notable study conducted by Mol, Bus, and de Jong (2020) investigated the effectiveness of interactive book reading in early education settings. The researchers found that engaging children in interactive reading sessions at home not only stimulated their print knowledge but also enhanced their home language skills. This study underscores the importance of incorporating interactive elements, such as asking open-ended questions and encouraging discussion, into home reading routines to maximize literacy outcomes (National Reading Panel, 2020). Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Bus, Van Ijzendoorn, and Pellegrini (2020) examined the intergenerational transmission of literacy through

joint book reading between parents and children. The findings revealed that joint book reading significantly contributed to children’s success in learning to read. This highlights the critical role of parental involvement and shared reading experiences in promoting literacy development at home. In addition to academic research, educational organizations such as the National Education Association (NEA) emphasize the positive impact of home reading strategies on children’s academic achievement and overall well-being. By incorporating regular reading sessions into daily routines and providing access to a diverse range of reading materials, families can create a supportive environment that fosters a love for reading and enhances literacy skills (Neuman Celano, 2021).

Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score.

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.32 with a p-value of .0211 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade one learners. This implies that the strategy of giving home reading assignments to grade one learners has increase their reading comprehension skills.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.32	0.0211	Significant

This finding is in line with the statement of Bobbit et al (2020) who said While home reading strategies offer numerous benefits for children’s literacy development, there are also some potential disadvantages or challenges associated with these approaches. Not all families have access to a wide variety of reading materials at home, which can restrict children’s exposure to diverse texts. Research by Neuman and Celano (2020) highlights disparities in access to books and literacy resources among socioeconomically disadvantaged families, which can hinder children’s literacy development (Paris et al., 2021). Home reading strategies play a vital role in children’s literacy development and academic success. These strategies, which involve reading activities conducted at home with parental involvement, provide numerous benefits that contribute to children’s language acquisition, cognitive development, and overall

literacy skills. Home reading exposes children to a wide range of words and concepts beyond their everyday language. Through exposure to diverse texts, children expand their vocabulary and develop a deeper understanding of language (Nagy Anderson, 2024).

Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade one Students

Table 4 highlights the test of home reading approach and reading comprehension skills of grade one learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.325 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy that would improve the reading comprehension skills of the learners. Reading is very important. If a child cannot read, he is expected to fail in other subject areas because he has to read also even in physical education subject.

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade 5 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
42	-4.22	0.3215	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

This finding aligns with the statement of de Jong (2020) who cited that home reading strategies play a crucial role in children’s literacy development. Reading at home provides children with opportunities to reinforce their reading skills, expand their vocabulary, and develop a lifelong love for reading. Shared reading involves parents or caregivers reading aloud to children while they follow along with the text. This strategy promotes language development,

comprehension skills, and a love for reading. It also provides opportunities for discussions about the story and vocabulary. Encouraging children to read independently at home helps improve fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary skills. Providing access to a variety of age-appropriate books and creating a comfortable reading environment are essential aspects of this strategy.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study seeks to determine the effect of the utilization of home language and reading ability of grade one pupils. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 2020). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study will be conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Division of Digos City. The subjects of this study will be the 60 grade one learners – 28 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 32 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the home reading approach is effective in improving the reading comprehension skills of the learners. When teacher give home reading assignment to learners, they start reading and reading until it becomes a part of their evening activity, thus, their reading comprehension skills start to develop.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions

are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade one learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Approaching Proficiency level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Proficient level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching reading should look for an approach that would tickle the interest of the learners to love reading as reading is a very important skills that every learner should have developed. To love reading needs a teacher that is appreciates reading. There must approaches that should initiated by reading teachers to transform learners into reading learners. The school heads should promote the love of reading in the campus by intensifying the reading centers, reading corners and the use of approaches that would entice learners to read. It is just a matter of motivating young learners to read by giving them varied opportunities to read. Once they developed the love of reading then literacy follows. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of home reading as an approach will be conducted paring with other variables to solve classroom-based problems.

5. References

- Afflerbach, P., Pearson, P. D., & Paris, S. G. (2020). Clarifying differences between reading skills and reading strategies. *The Reading Teacher*, 61(5), 364–373.
- Beck, I. L., McKeown, M. G., & Kucan, L. (2022). *Bringing words to life: Robust vocabulary instruction*. Guilford Press.

- Biancarosa, G., & Snow, C. E. (2020). Reading next—a vision for action and research in middle and high school literacy: A report to Carnegie Corporation of New York (2nd ed.) *Alliance for Excellent Education*.
- Biemiller, A., & Boote, C. (2020). An effective method for building meaning vocabulary in primary grades. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 98(1), 44–62.
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2020). Inside the black box: Raising standards through classroom assessment. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 80(2), 139–148.
- Bus, A. G., Van IJzendoorn, M. H., & Pellegrini, A. D. (2019). Joint book reading makes for success in learning to read: A meta-analysis on intergenerational transmission of literacy. *Review of Educational Research*, 65(1), 1–21.
- Cunningham, A. E., & Stanovich, K. E. (2021). Tracking the unique effects of print exposure in children: Associations with vocabulary, general knowledge, and spelling. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 83(2), 264–274.
- Desimone, L. M. (2020). Linking parent involvement with student achievement: Do race and income matter? *Journal of Educational Research*, 93(1), 11–30.
- Duke, N. K., & Pearson, P. D. (2022). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension. In A. E. Farstrup & S. J. Samuels (Eds.), *What research has to say about reading instruction* (3rd, pp. 205–242). International Reading Association.
- Gough, P. B., Hoover, W. A., & Peterson, C. L. (2016). Some observations on a simple view of reading. In C. Cornoldi & J. Oakhill (Eds.), *Reading comprehension difficulties: Processes and intervention* (pp. 1–13). Erlbaum.
- Guthrie, J. T., Wigfield, A., & Klauda, S. L. (2022). Adolescents’ engagement in reading: It matters. In S. L. Christenson, A. L. Reschly, & C. Wylie (Eds.), *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 253–280). Springer.
- Keene, E. O., & Zimmerman, S. (2017). *Mosaic of thought: The power of comprehension strategy instruction* (2nd). Heinemann.
- Kuo, L. J., Uchikoshi, Y., & Kim, H. Y. (2017). Bilingual parent-child home reading practices among immigrant families: Case studies in Japanese-English and Korean-English bilingualism. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 38(9), 797–812.
- McGeown, S. P., Goodwin, H., Henderson, N., & Wright, P. (2015). Gender differences in reading motivation: Does sex or gender identity provide a better account? *Journal of Research in Reading*, 38(2), 136–151.
- Mol, S. E., Bus, A. G., & de Jong, M. T. (2018). Interactive book reading in early education: A tool to stimulate print knowledge as well as oral language. *Review of Educational Research*, 78(4), 979–1007.
- Mol, S. E., Bus, A. G., de Jong, M. T., & Smeets, D. J. (2018). Added value of dialogic parent-child book readings: A meta-analysis. *Early Education and Development*, 19(1), 7–26.
- Nagy, W. E., & Anderson, R. C. (2024). How many words are there in printed school English? *Reading Research Quarterly*, 19(3), 304–330.
- National Education Association. (n.d.). Parental involvement in reading: Helping children succeed.
- National Reading Panel. (2020). Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction.

- Neuman, S. B., & Celano, D. (2021). Access to print in low-income and middle-income communities: An ecological study of four neighborhoods. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 36(1), 8–26.
- Norton, D. E. (2018). Multicultural children’s literature through the lens of critical literacy. *The Reading Teacher*, 67(2), 120–130.
- Oakhill, J., & Cain, K. (2022). The precursors of reading ability in young readers: Evidence from a four-year longitudinal study. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 16(2), 91–121.
- Paris, S. G., & Paris, A. H. (2021). Classroom applications of research on self-regulated learning. *Educational Psychologist*, 36(2), 89–101.
- Perfetti, C. A., Landi, N., & Oakhill, J. (2017). The acquisition of reading comprehension skill. In M. J. Snowling & C. Hulme (Eds.), *The science of reading: A handbook* (pp. 227–247). Blackwell.
- Pressley, M. (2022). Comprehension instruction: What makes sense now, what might make sense soon. *Reading Online*, 5(2).
- Senechal, M., LeFevre, J. A., Hudson, E., & Lawson, E. P. (2016). Knowledge of storybooks as a predictor of young children’s vocabulary. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 88(3), 520–536.
- Sénéchal, M., & LeFevre, J. A. (2022). Parental involvement in the development of children’s reading skill: A five-year longitudinal study. *Child Development*, 73(2), 445–460.
- Shaywitz, S. E., Shaywitz, B. A., Fletcher, J. M., & Escobar, M. D. (2018). Prevalence of reading disability in boys and girls: Results of the connecticut longitudinal study. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 281(16), 1573–1575.
- Tomlinson, C. A., & Allan, S. D. (2020). *Leadership for differentiating schools and classrooms*. ASCD.
- Whitehurst, G. J., Falco, F. L., Lonigan, C. J., Fischel, J. E., DeBaryshe, B. D., Valdez-Menchaca, M. C., & Caulfield, M. (2024). Accelerating language development through picture book reading. *Developmental Psychology*, 30(4), 484–490.